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Dream On

Dream

remains to be a dream
in the quiet night
where papers pile under dim light

Exhausted

but somewhere within,
a quiet fire starts to burn
and refuses to surrender

Returned

to the pages staring at her,
waiting for the first stroke of inspiration
whispering "dream on"

Sunrise

After endless nights and grinds
A witness, the non-stop burning light
Dreaming on....